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The Anchor Alexanders of Babylon II

PLATES 1–10

LLOYD W. H. TAYLOR*

Coinage bearing an anchor symbol and the name of Alexander was struck at the Babylon II mint under Seleukos in the period 309/8–304/3 BC. An estimated 93 tetradrachm obverse dies were commissioned for this coinage, which can be divided into three groups of issues. Die links, stylistic affinities, and a rapid succession of changes in mint conventions establish a robust relative chronology within and between the three groups. In this we can discern five stages of mint operation from recommissioning through to decline and closure. The latter is characterized by recutting of reverse dies from which the anchor symbol was erased following Seleukos's assumption of the royal title. In the course of the mint's development, a senior official designated by the Γ mint mark played an important role that appears to have continued with his transfer via Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis) to Seleukeia on the Tigris. Tentatively, this official is identified as Polyarchos, a *hyparch* in Babylonia who, accompanied by 1,000 troops, joined Seleukos when the latter returned to Babylonia in 312/11 BC.

* Independent scholar (lloyd_taylor@bigpond.com).

BACKGROUND

The Babylon II mint¹ was established by Seleukos in ca. 318/7 BC,² initially to strike an Alexandrine coinage in the name of Philip III Arrhidaios.³ The mint closed with Seleukos's flight to Egypt in 316 BC, only to be reestablished following his success in wresting control of Babylonia from Antigonid forces in the Babylonian war of 311/0–309/8 BC.⁴ The anchor Alexander coinage of Babylon II consists predominantly of tetradrachms, accompanied by a lesser volume of gold staters and small denomination silver, bearing the legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ⁵ (Price 3339–3364). These are united by the presence of the Seleukid anchor symbol displayed in the left field of the reverse, plus a number of mint controls, some of which are also shared with a group of contemporaneous Babylonian Ba'al/lion staters (SC 88) also struck at Babylon II. The coinage has a checkered history of attribution. Initially it was thought to have been struck at Arados under Antigonid control preceding the Battle of Ipsos in 301 BC.⁶ This attribution conflicted with the find locations of the coinage, predominantly in Babylonia and Mesopotamia, and the many mint control links to the Babylonian Ba'al/lion stater coinage.⁷ Subsequent study saw the coinage reattributed to Babylonia or Mesopotamia,⁸ after which *Seleucid Coins* attributed the coinage to the Babylonian satrapal mint, Babylon II, in the period ca. 311–305 BC.⁹ Most recently, it has been argued that the start of the anchor Alexander emission should

1. Also termed the "Native" or "Satrapal" mint reflecting the fact that it was under the direct control of the satrap of Babylonia. It also produced a Ba'al/lion coinage to sustain the local economy.

2. Dates are referenced to the Macedonian lunar calendar year which began in the Autumn; September/October of our Gregorian calendar.

3. SC 1.1, 39–50; L. W. H. Taylor, "From Triparadeisos to Ipsos: Seleukos I Nikator's Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia," *AJN* 27 (2015), 66–69.

4. J. E. McTavish, "A New Chronology for Seleucus Nikator's Wars from 311–308 B.C.E.," *Phoenix* 73 (2019), 1–2: 62–85; Taylor, "Triparadeisos," 68–69.

5. The one exception being Price 3340, SC 92, a gold stater on which the royal title is omitted.

6. *WSM*, 192–195.

7. M. J. Price, *The Coinage in the Name of Alexander the Great and Philip Arrhidaeus* (London: British Museum/Swiss Numismatic Society, 1991), 415–416 expressed strong reservations about Newell's attribution of the coinage to Arados, stating that it is "very unlikely" but then proceeded to adhere to Newell's attribution, creating confusion that persists to this day.

8. A. Houghton, "Some Alexander Coinages of Seleucus I with Anchors," *Mediterranean Archaeology* 4 (1991), 99, and 109–115 (MA 4 in the catalogue) proposed an eastern origin, Babylonia, or Mesopotamia.

9. SC 1.1, 43–48.

be downdated to no earlier than 309/8 BC,¹⁰ after which Babylon II struck two coinages, the Ba'al/lion staters (SC 88) and the anchor Alexanders (SC 80, 92–100 and 105). Both bear the Γ primary mint control on a majority of the types.

Although the attribution and general chronology of the anchor Alexanders now rest on a firm foundation, the exact sequence of issues, their internal relationships and precise dating remains uncertain. Many new specimens of the coinage have appeared in the 30 years since the publication of the die study that underpins the current interpretation of the coinage.¹¹ Based on a larger sample, the following die study of gold staters and tetradrachms clarifies internal relationships in the coinage and provides a basis for the interpretation of the mint's operation. The catalogue of coins underpinning this is detailed at the end of this paper. Coins denoted by an asterisk against the catalogue entry are illustrated on Plates 1–10.¹²

DISCUSSION

The coinage is categorized into three groups, each based on recurrent primary mint controls, plus die links that define the association of specific sequence types identified on the basis of different secondary mint controls. The latter are designated by a digit following the primary group identifier (Table 1). The group numbering does not imply a relative chronological order. Rather, it reflects the relative magnitude of the mintage of each, from the largest (Group 1) to the smallest (Group 3). Within each group, the sequence is well constrained by die links between types (Table 2, fold-out) accompanied by a clear progression in the sequence of mint controls. The gold staters are positioned within the sequence by reference to the mint controls on their tetradrachm counterparts (Table 1).

Table 1. Sequence types and concordance.

	Price	SC	Controls
Group 1			
1.1	3339	80	— $\text{\textcircled{\Gamma}}$
1.2	3342A	94.1	club/ Φ Γ
1.3	3344A	94.2C	$\text{\textcircled{\Gamma}}$ Γ

10. C. C. Lorber, "A Hoard of Tetradrachms of Alexander III and Philip III, November 2003," *AJN* 27 (2015), 29–40; Taylor, "Triparadeisos," 68–69; L. W. H. Taylor, "Susa Mint: 311–301 BC," *KOINON* III (2020), 18–42.

11. Houghton, "Anchors," Groups I, II, III and part of Group IV.

12. For the few obverse dies that are not illustrated, the reader is referred to the original publication in which they appear, as noted in the catalogue.

Table 1 (continued). Sequence types and concordance.

	Price	SC	Controls
Group 1			
1.4 (stater)	3340	92	☒ ⌈
1.5	3341	94.2b	☒ ⌈
1.6	3342	—	☒ ⌈
1.7	3343	—	A ⌈
1.8	3344	94.2a	Ⓐ ⌈
1.9	—	—	☒ ⌈
1.10 (stater)	3348	93.1	☒ ⌈
1.11	3349	94.3d	☒ ⌈
1.12	3346	94.3c	NE ⌈
1.13	—	94.3c	Ⓝ ⌈
1.14	3347	94.3c	Ⓝ ⌈
1.15	3351	94.3b	Ⓜ ⌈
1.16 (stater)	3352	93.2	⌈ Ⓜ
1.17	3353	94.3a	Ⓜ ⌈
1.18	—	94.3d	☒ ⌈
1.19	—	—	Ⓝ ⌈
Group 2			
2.1 (stater)	—	—	Ⓐ Ⓜ
2.2	—	94.6a	Ⓐ M
2.3	—	—	Ⓐ M
2.4	3359	94.6b	A M
2.5	3358	94.6b	Λ M
2.6	—	94.6c	Ω M
2.7	3356	94.6c	Ⓜ M
2.8	3350	—	Ⓐ A
2.9	—	94.4	☒ A
2.10	—	—	Λ Ⓜ
2.11	—	94.5	— Ⓜ

Shading denotes types struck from reverse dies on which the anchor symbol was erased.

Table 1 (continued). Sequence types and concordance.

	Price	SC	Controls
Group 2			
2.12	—	94.5	— □
2.13	—	94.4	— A
Group 3			
3.1	3363	105.1	⋈ ⚠
3.2	3363A	105.2	⋈ ⚠ ⚡
3.3	—	105.2	— ⚡

Shading denotes types struck from reverse dies on which the anchor symbol was erased.

Group 1 is characterized by the □ mint control on all but the initial issue, which bears a complex monogram built around the letter □. On the last reverse dies of Group 1 the anchor symbol was erased. Group 2 initially bears the letter M as the primary mint control, which is then displaced by the letter A, the latter elevated from a secondary control position in the left field to the primary control location beneath the throne. The final issues were struck from dies on which the Group 2 controls were mostly overcut with the □ control of Group 1. This recutting was accompanied by the erasure of the anchor symbol from the dies. Group 3 is of small size. It consists of a few tetradrachm types bearing the ⋈ and ⚠ mint controls on all but the last issue, from which these controls were erased from the die together with the anchor symbol.

Four factors serve to establish the association and relative chronology of the issues across the three groups. Firstly, a chronological progression in the mint's convention for the placement of the secondary mint control relative to the anchor is apparent in Group 1 (Table 3, below). On the early issues of Group 1, and all of Group 3, the secondary mint control is placed above the anchor symbol. Subsequently, the secondary control is placed below the anchor in Group 1. Then, in the latter part of Group 1, midway through the striking of 1.11 and 1.13, the secondary control is placed to the right of the anchor, before Zeus's legs (suffixes "a" and "b" distinguish the change in 1.11 and 1.13). In contrast, throughout Group 2 the secondary mint control is placed to the right of the anchor.

Closely associated with this change in Group 1 is the introduction of a footstool beneath Zeus's feet, which previously rested on a ground line. This occurs midway through the emission 1.11 and 1.13, coincident with the change in placement of the secondary mint control. In Group 2 a similar development occurs with the start of 2.9, while in Group 3 Zeus's feet rest exclusively on a ground line (Table 3).

Table 3. Conventions.

Type	Mint control relative to anchor			Feet of Zeus rest on	
	Above	Below	Inside to r.	Ground line	Footstool
1.3-1.8					
3.1-3.2					
1.9-1.11a					
1.12-1.13a					
1.13a (last)					
2.2-2.8					
2.9					
1.11b					
1.13b-1.17					
<i>Recycled dies</i>					
2.10					
<i>Anchor erased</i>					
1.18-1.19					
<i>Anchor and l. field control erased</i>					
2.11-2.12			<i>erased</i>		
2.13			<i>erased</i>		
3.3	<i>erased</i>				

In addition to these varying conventions, an obverse die-link between Groups 1 and 2 establishes a close chronological relationship between types 1.11 and 2.9 (Table 2, fold-out).¹³ Die A64 was transferred from issue 2.9 to 1.11b where it exhibits an advanced state of wear. This establishes the contemporaneity of types 2.9 and 1.11. Finally, the erasure of the anchor symbol on the last components of all three groups serves to indicate that these issues were contemporaneous. On the dies with erased anchors the mint control and iconographic conventions are mixed, reflecting the recycling of dies from earlier periods of the mint's operation. Together these factors establish the relative chronology of the three groups as summarized in Table 4 (see fold-out) and detailed further below.

13. Dies are numbered according to the group for which they were commissioned and initially put into use. A64 saw its earliest use in Group 2, before being transferred in a worn state to Group 1.

Gold Staters

The Group 1 gold staters (1.4, 1.10, 1.10a and 1.16) were struck from four obverse dies. A previously undocumented type, 1.10a, is characterized by the variant placement of the mint controls to the left and right of Nike compared to 1.10, to which it is obverse die linked by Av3. Both are linked by the same obverse die to type 1.16. Unknown to earlier studies is a Group 2 stater (2.1) which bears the mint marks \mathfrak{A} and \mathfrak{M} . The attribution of this stater to Group 2 relies on both stylistic affinity and the progression of mint controls observed in the tetradrachm sequence. The style and detail of obverse die Av5, from which it was struck, is so close to Av2 (type 1.10) that both are likely to have been engraved by the same hand (Pl. 1, 2 and 7). This suggests that types 2.1 and 1.10 are close contemporaries, originating in the same mint.

The \mathfrak{M} monogram on 2.1 appears to have been the precursor to the M primary mint control found on tetradrachm types 2.2–2.7. Significantly, this monogram was recut over the letter A, still faintly visible beneath the monogram. The A mint mark initially appears as a secondary mint control on tetradrachm type 2.4, then to displace the M mint mark as the primary control on 2.8 and 2.9. The overcutting of A by \mathfrak{M} on 2.1 may reflect either uncertainty, or changes to the authority levels of mint officials at the start of Group 2. It is notable that the \mathfrak{A} mint mark on the 2.1 stater is also found on the 1.8 tetradrachms, indicating again the close relationship between Groups 1 and 2. Moreover, as argued below, it is likely that the \mathfrak{A} mint mark was progressively simplified to the letter A, with the inference that these two marks designate the same mint official, one who moved from the early Group 1 striking line to oversee the Group 2 mintage from its outset.

Group 1 Tetradrachms

A total of 45 obverse tetradrachm dies are identified in Group 1, including A64, which is shared with Group 2. The sequence opens with a tetradrachm (Price 3339; SC 80) struck from an obverse die that was used previously in 316 BC to strike an issue in the name of Philip III (Price P153; SC 79).¹⁴ The reuse of an obverse die from a Philip III issue on the reopening of the mint finds a direct parallel in the first of the anchor Alexanders struck at Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis) in Babylonia.¹⁵ This practice has a symbolic, or ritual character, also hinted at by the changing placement of the torch symbol which was displaced by the anchor

14. F. Duyrat, *Arados hellénistique: Étude historique et monétaire* (Beirut: Institut Français du Proche-Orient, 2005), Group V, Série 8, 980, obverse die D228.

15. Taylor, "Triparadeisos" 46, fig. 1; SC Ad39.4 (Philip III) die linked (A18) to SC 67.1.

insignia of Seleukos, and relegated to a position beneath the feet of Zeus. The anchor insignia had its origins in Seleukos's navarchy in the period 315–312 BC.¹⁶ On his return to Babylonia, its presence served to identify Seleukos as the issuing authority for coinage struck in the name of Alexander. The anchor on type 1.1 indicates that this issue postdates his return to Babylonia. This understanding negates the previously proposed dating of SC 80 to 315–311 BC,¹⁷ as an Antigonid issue from Babylon II.¹⁸ It reverts to Price's interpreted date range for the issue, ca. 311–ca. 300 BC.

The significance of this initial issue is emphasized by the presence of the mint control, further linking type 1.1 to the last issue in the name of Philip III, although this monogram is now in the position of the primary control beneath the throne of Zeus, reflecting the elevation of the official designated by this monogram. In the balance of Group 1, it appears that this complex monogram is simplified to a single letter, Γ. On the following issue, 1.2, a supplementary symbol, the club of Herakles, accompanied by two letters ΦΙ is found beneath the anchor insignia of Seleukos. This is the only such occurrence in the coinage. The club beneath the anchor might have been an extension of the symbolism associated with type 1.1, although its meaning is not clear to us.

In placing the primary mint control beneath the throne of Zeus, the mint maintained the convention established during Seleukos's first satrapy. However, with the introduction of the anchor symbol as a prominent feature in the left field of the reverse, the options for the placement of a secondary mint control (a monogram or a letter) relative to the symbol were several (Table 3, above), and changed through time. Following type 1.2, the secondary mint control was placed above and to the left of the anchor symbol (1.3–1.8). This permitted a larger anchor symbol, but positioned the mint mark in the outer left field, an area prone to be struck off flan. Subsequently, the secondary control migrated to a position beneath the anchor, necessitating a reduction in the size of the symbol (1.9, 1.11a–1.13a). Then, the anchor symbol was given greater prominence, by placing the secondary mint control to the right of the anchor shank, placing the control immediately before Zeus's legs (1.11b, 1.13b–1.17). This was closely associated with the introduction of a new device in the iconography. In the first half of the Group 1 sequence, Zeus's feet rest on a ground line. With the removal

16. L. W. H. Taylor, "The Susa Wreath Group Alexanders: The First Step in the Transformation of an Anchor Seal to a Dynastic Emblem," *KOINON* II (2019), 63–82.

17. *Seleucid Coins* 1.1, 39, expressed reservations with the proposed dating to 315–311 BC.

18. O. D. Hoover, "A Necessary Evil: Alexandrine Coinages and the Tension of Personal Kingship in the Seleucid Empire," in *Les Alexandres après Alexandre: histoire d'une monnaie commune. Actes du colloque international, Athènes, 23–24 mai 2014*, ed. S. Kremydi, M.-C. Marcellesi (Athens: Institut de recherches historiques, 2019), 131–145.

of the secondary mint control from beneath the anchor to a position to the right of the anchor, a footstool was inserted between the ground line and the feet of Zeus. This device persists throughout the balance of Group 1. The last example of 1.13a (no. 99) is the only transitional coin in this pattern of change, marking the first appearance of the footstool in the Group 1 sequence, while the left field mint control remains beneath the anchor stock. Notably, these changes coincide with the introduction into Group 1 of the Group 2 die A64 from type 2.9. (Table 4, fold-out). The multiplicity of die links between types 1.11–1.19 (Table 2, above) suggest that these were struck in a progression of parallel striking involving up to three anvils (Table 4, fold-out). On the last of Group 1 issues (1.18 and 1.19) the anchor is erased from reverse dies previously used to strike 1.11b and 1.14 (Table 4, fold-out).

Group 2 Tetradrachms

Twenty-one obverse tetradrachm dies are identified in Group 2, in a sequence that is tightly die-linked (Table 4, fold-out). Throughout Group 2 the secondary mint control is placed inside and to right of the anchor symbol. However, there is a progression in the iconographic convention of Zeus's feet resting initially on a ground line, followed by the introduction of a footstool beneath his feet at the start of type 2.9. Based on these observations it appears that the convention for the placement of secondary control inside and to the right of the anchor was developed and implemented initially in Group 2, then to be adopted in Group 1, accompanied by a footstool beneath the feet of Zeus (Table 4, fold-out).

Obverse tetradrachm die A64 which links Group 1 and 2 was probably the last one commissioned for Group 2 notwithstanding the identification of another Group 2 die, A65, among the later anchor-erased coinage struck from recycled Group 2 dies. The first occurrence of A65 in the catalogue is on type 2.13, paired to a reverse die that prior to recutting was used for type 2.9. On type 2.13, die A65 is moderately worn, so that it is probable that A65 was used previously in the Group 2 sequence, but is not represented in our sample of the preceding issues.

The A64 die-link between types 2.9 and 1.11b together with the near identical character of the obverse stater dies used for issues 2.1 (Av5) and 1.10 (Av2) establishes the relative chronology of the two groups. Group 2 was struck contemporaneously with Group 1 issues 1.10 and 1.11a–1.13a. In this we have evidence of two lines of parallel striking, each under the primary oversight of a different mint official, designated by Γ in the case of Group 1, and M succeeded by A in the case of Group 2. With the transfer of die A64 into Group 1 the primary Group 2

Figure 1. Detail of catalogue no. 235.

sequence ceased. Later types in the sequence, 2.10 and 2.11, were struck from a recycled Group 2 reverse die with a Γ mint control, accompanied by subsidiary letters P and K, recut over the M control resulting a complex monogram in which vestiges of the original mint control remain (Fig. 1). On type 2.12 the Γ control was recut over the A control from the latter part of Group 2, while on type 2.13 the A control remains intact, although the anchor and associated left field control were erased from the reverse die. Plausibly, the recycled Group 2 obverse dies, A60 and A65, accompanied by reverse dies P183–P186 were transferred to the Group 1 striking line accompanying die A64, eventually to be recycled with the reverse dies recut for use at the end of Group 1.

Reinforcing the association of Group 2 with Group 1 is the fact that both share five mint controls (\mathfrak{B} , A, \mathfrak{P} , \mathfrak{A} , and Γ) at differing times in each sequence. There is a progression in the development of the secondary mint control in Group 2, from \mathfrak{B} (2.1) to \mathfrak{A} (2.2), then \mathfrak{A} (2.3) and finally the letter A (2.4). The latter is also rendered as Λ on the two reverse dies of type 2.5. These are paired to obverse dies A46 and A47 which link 2.5 to 2.4. Wear on these obverse dies indicates that the Λ -bearing reverse dies of 2.5 were interspersed with the A mint mark reverse dies of 2.4; an indication that the Λ is but an engraving variant of the letter A.¹⁹ In this progression of mint marks it appears that all forms designate one and the same mint official, expressed in a trend to simplification of his mark. Some corrections to the reading of mint controls by prior scholars are noted in this progression. Most significant is the correction to the reading of the left field mint control on type 2.2 (SC 94.6a) which was recorded previously as \mathfrak{B} , but in reality is \mathfrak{A} . The three dots aligned along the right limb of the letter A superficially resemble a ligate B. Obverse die linked to 2.2 is a variant of the same control on which the dots are replaced by two dashes \mathfrak{A} (type 2.3). Despite the appearance of these variant forms, the \mathfrak{B} mint control link between Groups 1 and 2 is maintained unequivocally with the identification of the 2.1 gold stater which bears the \mathfrak{B} mint mark found on the 1.8 tetradrachm. In this we can infer

19. The same variant engraving of the letter A also occurs in the legend of the tetradrachms.

the transfer of the mint official designated by \mathfrak{A} on type 1.8 to Group 2 for the striking of 2.1–2.5 in which he acted as a secondary official, after which he was elevated to a primary official role in the striking of issues 2.8 and 2.9. A further interchange of controls marks, and inferred the movement of the mint officials between Groups 1 and 2 is also noted with another two mint controls, \mathfrak{P} found on 2.7 and 1.16–1.17 and \mathfrak{N} present on 2.9, 1.10, 1.11, and 1.18.

Group 3 Tetradrachms

The sample of Group 3 consists of seven tetradrachms struck from two obverse dies. In detail these are so close to some of the Philip III issues of Babylon II that they must have been cut by the same die engraver, one employed at the mint during Seleukos's first satrapy.²⁰ The Group 3 mint controls, \mathfrak{K} , \mathfrak{A} , and \mathfrak{E} ²¹ set it apart from Groups 1 and 2. However, reinforcing the association of Group 3 with Babylon II is the \mathfrak{K} mint mark that is also found on some of the Seleukid lion staters (SC 88.5–88.6) from Babylon II. As with Groups 1 and 2, the last of Group 3 was struck from a reverse die from which the anchor symbol was erased.

On all the reverse dies of Group 3 the feet of Zeus rest on a ground line, while the location of a secondary mint control is above the anchor symbol. This is consistent with the conventions observed on Group 1 issues 1.3–1.8. It suggests that 3.1 and 3.2 were the product of a short-lived striking operation in parallel with the early Group 1 sequence (Table 4, fold-out).

Obverse styles

Ten obverse styles can be recognized in the tetradrachm obverse dies (Table 5, below). In many cases it appears that each of these styles originated from the hand of a single die engraver, although within the subjective uncertainty that attaches to such a determination more than one engraver may be represented in some of the styles.

20. See Duyrat, *Arados*, Group V, Série 9; pl. 12, 997 (D232) for a closely styled obverse, possibly from the same die engraver as that which cut A66 and A67.

21. The reading of this mint mark is doubtful. Both examples are well worn and corroded with the result that the Δ - Σ component is not determined with any confidence. However, I have followed the SC determination in preference to proposing an alternative in which the Δ - Σ component is absent.

Table 5. Distribution of tetradrachm obverse styles.

Style	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
1	A1, A2, A44	—	—
2	—	—	A66, A67
3	A3–A9	—	—
4	A10	—	—
5	A11–A19, A30	—	—
6	—	A45–A52, A54–A58, A60	—
7	A20–A22, A24–A26, A64	A61–A64	—
8	A23, A28, A29, A32–A41	A65	—
9	A27, A31	—	—
10	A42–A43	A53, A59	—

The work of die engravers responsible for the earliest dies of Group 1 and Group 3, can be found in the preceding Babylon II issues in the name of Philip III, dating to the first satrapy of Seleukos, while issues 2.2–2.7 possess a distinctively crude style (style 6). This suggests that less-skilled engravers were dedicated to the cutting of the initial Group 2 tetradrachm dies. Although this crude style persists until the end of type 2.8 it is joined by dies cut in styles 7, 8 and 10, also found in Group 1. It appears that Group 1 die engravers were progressively engaged in cutting dies for the last of the Group 2 sequence. The dies of type 2.9 (A61–A64) are exclusively from the hands of engravers also engaged in Group 1. In this pattern we see the displacement of a dedicated engraving resource in Group 2 by engravers from Group 1 during the mintage of types 2.7–2.9.

Erasure of the anchor symbol

The origin and significance of the anchor insignia and the motivation for its temporary removal from the coinage of Seleukos have been outlined in previous studies.²² It was a temporary action that preceded the myth-making of Seleukos's ascent to power, which saw the anchor mythologized as a sign of divine sanction, only then to be reinstated on coinage from the early third century BC. The temporary removal of the anchor insignia of Seleukos from coinage was closely associated with the earliest issuance in his own name. This is borne out by some examples struck at Uncertain Mint 6A that bear the legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΣΕΛΕΥΚΟΥ struck from a recut die with anchor erasure (Pl. 10, D and E),

22. Taylor, "Triparadeisos"; Taylor, "Wreath Group"; Taylor, "Susa."

Figure 2. Detail of erased left field (cat. nos. 150 and 235).

obverse die-linked to both anchor-bearing and anchor-erased strikes in the name of Alexander (Pl. 10, B and C).

Unknown to previous scholars,²³ the erasure of the Seleukid anchor symbol from reverse dies bearing the name of Alexander also occurred at the Susa mint (Pl. 10, G, H and J)²⁴ in addition to previously documented examples from Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A (Pl. 10, A–E). The Susa examples establish beyond doubt that this was a coordinated action across three mints in two provinces. They dispel the notion of *Seleucid Coins* that this may have been the result of Antigonid action during the Babylonian war, for Susa was never under Antigonid control after it was annexed by Seleukos in 311 BC.

The erasure of the anchor from dies at the Babylonian and Susa mints was performed carefully but imperfectly, with the result that vestiges, or ghost outlines of the anchor are observed on coins struck from these dies. Abrasion resurfacing of the left field of the die to erase the anchor symbol results in a slightly elevated area on the coin strike, often showing a ghost outline of the anchor. This was employed on some of the recycled dies at Uncertain Mint 6A and Susa (Pl. 10). However, at Babylon II an additive resurfacing process appears to have been undertaken, whereby the primary elements of the left field were filled in, albeit incompletely, and the left field roughly resurfaced. In two cases the stock of the anchor on the die was incompletely filled leaving a partial imprint on the strike (Fig. 2), although the rest of the anchor is absent. Infill might have been undertaken using a small amount of molten bronze resulting in the irregular edges on the infilled surface, subsequently scraped and ground away to achieve a smoother surface.

23. SC 1.1, 6: "During the period ca. 311–305 the anchor symbol is also found on the Ba'al/lion series of Babylon and on the earliest tetradrachm issue of Susa, but no erasures have been reported from either of these coinages."

24. Taylor, "Susa," pls. 3–4.

STATISTICS

The sample of gold staters represented in the catalogue is insufficient for estimation of the original number of gold stater dies used at the mint. The sample of 238 tetradrachms (n) in which 67 obverse dies (d) are identified is a significant sample ($n/d=3.6$) of the obverse dies with a statistical coverage (C_{est}) of 0.88 (Table 6). Using Esty's geometrical model,²⁵ it is calculated that 93 tetradrachm dies (± 11 dies at the 95% confidence level) were used in the mintage. These might have struck approximately 1.86 million tetradrachms,²⁶ equivalent to 1,223 Attic talents of silver at an average weight of 17.1 grams per tetradrachm. The five gold stater dies identified in the catalogue could have struck approximately 50,000 staters, the equivalent of 16.54 Attic talents of gold or 165.4 Attic talents of silver equivalent. This would bring the value of the Babylon II anchor Alexander mint-age to around 1,388 Attic talents of silver equivalent—a significant emission.

Table 6. Tetradrachm statistics.

Group	Sample (n)	Observed dies (d)	Singletons (d_1)	Estimated original dies (D_{est})	Statistical Coverage (C_{est})	95% Confidence Interval
1	144	44.5	18	64.4	0.88	55.1–75.4
2	87	20.5	5	26.8	0.94	22.7–31.7
3	7	2	1	2.8	0.86	1.6–5.3
Total	238	67	24	93.3	0.89	83.2–104.6

METROLOGY

The weight of the seven gold staters in the catalogue is tightly distributed around 8.6 g (range 8.52–8.64 g), the Attic weight standard for gold staters. The statistics of the tetradrachm weight distribution are summarized in Table 7. There is no statistically significant difference in the weight distribution of each of the three groups. The weight distribution of the total sample plotted on Figure 3 exhibits a strong negative skew associated with the appreciable number of worn coins in the sample. However, a well-developed modal cluster centred around 17.1 (± 0.5) g defines the intended weight standard to which the tetradrachm coinage was struck. This slightly reduced Attic weight standard is consistent with that

25. W. W. Esty, "The Geometric Model for Estimating the Number of Dies," in *Quantifying Monetary Supplies in Greco-Roman Times*, ed. F. de Callataÿ. (Bari: Edipuglia, 2011), 46, formula (1).

26. F. de Callataÿ, "Quantifying Monetary Production in Greco-Roman Times: A General Frame," in *Quantifying Monetary Supplies in Greco-Roman Times*, ed. F. de Callataÿ. (Bari: Edipuglia, 2011), 7–29.

Figure 3. Tetradrachm weight distribution.

identified in the other Alexandrine coinages of Seleukos that were struck in the last decade of the fourth century BC.²⁷

Table 7. Tetradrachm weights.

Group	<i>n</i>	Mean (g)	Median (g)	Mode (g)	σ (g)
1	143	16.87	16.99	16.99	0.35
2	84	16.86	17.02	17.10	0.41
3	7	16.82	16.85	—	0.30
1–3	234	16.87	16.99	17.00	0.37

CHRONOLOGY

Seleucid Coins proposed that the anchor Alexanders were struck in the period ca. 311–305 BC.²⁸ However, two Babylonian hoards documented since that publication indicate that downdating the start of coinage is justified. The first, found in 2001, consisted of a majority of Seleukid Ba'al/lion staters (SC 88), mint control linked to the Babylon II anchor Alexanders. It suggests that the Seleukid Ba'al/lion component was struck in the period 308/7–303/2 BC to fund the

27. Taylor, "Tripasideis," 54–56; Taylor, "Wreath Group," 76; Taylor "Susa," 32–33.

28. SC 1.1, 43–49.

construction of Seleukeia on the Tigris.²⁹ This implies a similar chronology for the control-linked anchor Alexanders bearing the Γ mint control. Another hoard of Alexandrine tetradrachms found in the vicinity of Babylon in 2003, buried in ca. 309 BC, indicates that the anchor Alexanders most probably commenced after this date.³⁰

Indirect evidence for the downdating of the start of the anchor Alexanders is found in the output of the Susa mint (Susa Groups 5 and 6). This mint represented a source of new coinage for Seleukos's campaign during the Babylonian War³¹ while Babylon remained under Antigonid control.³² Only with the conclusion of the Babylonian War could Seleukos reestablish mint operations in Babylon. The Susa Group 5 and 6 issues carry a number of symbols, with the anchor symbol only emerging on the last of the issues, and then accompanied by another symbol. They predate the adoption of the anchor insignia as the preeminent identifying insignia of Seleukos as the issuer of coinage he struck in the name of Alexander. The transfer of primary Seleukid mint operations from Susa to Babylon after the war is identified with the end of the Susa Groups 5 and 6 emissions, followed by a hiatus in mint operations, preceding a small mintage of anchor Alexanders (Susa Group 7) struck from five obverse dies, which commenced around 304/3 BC. The last of these were struck from dies with anchor erasures (Pl. 10, F–J). These new findings are congruent with the results of an earlier analysis of the operation of Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis) in Babylonia, which issued a sequence of anchor Alexanders (Series II) in the period ca. 307/6–304/3 BC.³³ This ended with a number of issues with anchor erasures, the precursor to a substantive emission bearing the name of Seleukos (Series V) including four issues struck from a recycled and multiply recut reverse die on which the anchor was erased (Pl. 10, A–E).

The numismatic evidence across the mints of Babylonia and Susiana indicates that the Babylon II mint was reestablished no earlier than 309/8 BC, while the erasure of the anchor insignia from reverse dies was associated with the acclamation of Seleukos's kingship on return from his eastern *anabasis* in ca. 304/3 BC. The latter would have necessitated a settling of military accounts, accompanied

29. P. Iossif and C. Lorber, "Marduk and the Lion," in *Liber Amicorum Tony Hackens*, ed. G. Moucharte et al. (Louvain-la-Neuve: Association de numismatique professeur Marcel Hoc, 2007), 345–363.

30. Lorber, "Hoard."

31. Taylor, "Wreath Group"; Taylor, "Susa."

32. R. J. van der Spek, "Seleukos, Self-Appointed General (*Strategos*) of Asia (311–305 B.C.) and the Satrapy of Babylon." In *The Age of the Successors and the Creation of the Hellenistic Kingdoms (323–276 B.C.)*, ed. H. Hauben and A. Meeus (Leuven: Peeters, 2014), 327–337.

33. Taylor, "Triparadeisos."

by preparations for the major military campaign into Asia Minor, which culminated in the decisive Battle of Ipsos in 301 BC. Undoubtedly, the mintage of an extensive anchor Alexander coinage at three mints in Babylonia and Susiana was directed to military expenditure. This was accomplished in a number of parallel issues, indicative of a compressed time frame for the mintage. In the case of Babylon II, almost half of the emission (based on die count) appears to have been struck in parallel, shortly preceding the closure of the mint in ca. 304/3 BC.

INTERPRETATION

The die study establishes five stages of development in the operation of the mint during the striking of the anchor Alexanders (Table 8, below). Stage 1 marked the reestablishment of the mint after a hiatus of at least eight years, using mint workers from its previous operation. This was accompanied by the initial issuance of a symbolic, or ritual coinage using an obverse die from the last of the Philip III issues, followed by the engraving of new dies by engravers that had been engaged previously at the mint during the first satrapy of Seleukos. Stage 1 included types 1.1, 1.2 and possibly 3.1 and 3.2, although it appears more likely based on the placement of the secondary mint controls that the latter fall into early Stage 2. Stage 2 primarily involved the striking of coinage from seven tetradrachm obverse dies, plus a stater obverse die all under the primary oversight of the mint official designated by the Γ mint control. It is likely that early in Stage 2 the small Group 3 coinage was minted; possibly struck in a separate workshop, indicated by the differing mint control suite to that found on the primary Stage 2 sequence.

Stage 3 marks an expansion in the mint's productivity to two substantial lines of striking, probably separate workshops under the oversight of different primary officials. The need for latter might have been prompted by the substantial mintage of Ba'al/lion staters issued from the mint³⁴ under the oversight of the Γ official, in addition to his duties in the striking of Group I anchor Alexanders. At least 31 tetradrachm obverse dies, plus four stater dies, were used in this stage. An exchange of mint workers between the workshops is apparent in the interchange of secondary control marks and the introduction of die engravers from Group 1 to Group 2. From its outset the Group 2 workshop established the convention of placing the secondary mint control inside and to the right of the anchor symbol in contrast to Group 1, which experimented with a succession of placement conventions before adopting the Group 2 convention. Com-

34. Iossif and Lorber, "Marduk," Series A-F, nos. 42-147; SC 88. Note that in the "Marduk" publication the Π mint mark has been incorrectly conflated with the Γ mint mark found on the pre-Seleukid Ba'al/lion staters.

mencing with the last of issue 2.4, three engravers from the Group 1 pool of engravers were progressively introduced into Group 2 so that by issue 2.9 only engravers formerly represented in Group 1 are to be found. Simultaneously, the Group 1 production line was expanded to include an additional anvil, striking types 1.12–1.13a. With this parallel striking arrangement firmly established in Group 1, the Group 2 striking ceased and the surviving dies from Groups 2 were transferred with die A64 to the Group 1 workshop, ending Stage 3 of the mint's operation.

The start of Stage 4 marked the consolidation of the mint's operation under the one senior official, designated by the \square mint control. Possibly this consolidation was facilitated by a wind down in the mintage of the Ba'al/lion staters which saw the \square official dedicated solely to oversight of the Group 1 emission. If so, this marked the completion of the primary construction effort funded by the Ba'al/lion stater mintage associated with the foundation of Seleukeia on Tigris.³⁵ This saw an intensive period of parallel striking, probably using three anvils to synchronously strike types 1.11b, 1.13b–1.17 from at least 27 obverse tetradrachm dies. Consolidation saw the conventions that were developed in Group 2 adopted in Group 1, resulting in the placement of the secondary control inside and to the right of the anchor symbol, accompanied by the introduction of a footstool beneath the feet of Zeus.

Stages 3 and 4 represents more than 80 percent of the total mintage. Used in continuous parallel striking on at least two anvils the 58 obverse dies used in this period could have been expended in around 6 months of striking activity.³⁶ Therefore, it is conceivable that Stages 3 and 4 of the mint's operation were completed in less than one year. Any more time than this would obviate the requirement for parallel striking, for the same output could have been achieved by continuous serial striking in little more than a year. In Stages 3 and 4 we see evidence that argues for a compressed period of striking for the bulk of the anchor Alexander coinage of Babylon II.

Stage 5 of the mint's operation is defined by the use of reverse dies from which the anchor was erased. The dies used in this stage originated from all three groups, recycled, and reverse recut for use under the supervision of the mint official designated by the \square mint control. This marks a rapid decline in the resources of the mint, preceding the closure of Babylon II and the consolidation

35. Iossif and Lorber, "Marduk"

36. Assuming an average obverse die productivity of 20,000 coins and a maximum average daily striking rate of 3,000 coins per anvil proposed by Callataÿ, "Quantifying," and F. de Callataÿ, *L'histoire des guerres mithridatiques vue par les monnaies* (Louvain-la-Neuve: Département d'archéologie et d'histoire de l'art, séminaire de numismatique Marcel Hoc, 1997).

of all Babylonian mint operations at the new foundation of Seleukeia on the Tigris, located about 50 km to the northeast of Babylon.

Table 8. Stages of mint operation.

Stage	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
1 Recommissioning (ca. 307/8 BC)	1.1–1.2 2 dies	—	—
2 Early operation	1.3–1.9 7 dies	—	3.1–3.2 2 dies
3 Expansion	1.11a–1.13a 10 dies	2.1–2.9 21 dies	—
4 Consolidation	1.11b 1.13b–1.17 27 dies	—	—
5 Decline and closure (ca. 304/3 BC)	1.18–1.19 2 recycled dies	2.10–2.13 2 recycled dies	3.3 1 recycled die

Types 2.10 and 2.11 provide insight into the sequence of decisions in closing the mint. Type 2.10 was struck from recycled dies (A60/P183) immediately prior to the removal of the anchor symbol. Die A60 was previously used to strike the 2.8 issue, while P183 was previously used to strike type 2.5. The preexisting control beneath the throne was recut (Fig 1, above), while the Λ mint mark and anchor symbol were left intact in the left field. Subsequently, on issues 2.11 struck from the same die set as 2.10, the reverse was further modified by the erasure of the anchor symbol and the accompanying mint mark. From this sequence of events it appears that the decision was taken to close the mint, leading to the reuse of old dies in the final stage of the mint's operation. Shortly thereafter, the decision was taken to eliminate the anchor symbol from the reverse. The closure of Babylon II was accompanied by the transfer of officials to other mints. This is recorded in the coinage of Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis) in Babylonia (Table 9, below).

The officials designated by the mint controls A , A and \square appear successively in the first Uncertain Mint 6A issues to bear the name of Seleukos. Two of these, A and \square are associated with a multiply recut, anchor-erased reverse die on which the name of Seleukos was engraved. (Pl. 10, E). Coins bearing these controls were struck as the mint transformed into a mobile military mint attached to the army on its deployment from Opis into Asia Minor preceding the Battle of Ipsos in 301 BC. Subsequently, the B and \square mint controls are found on some of the

Zeus/elephant chariot coinage (SC 130) of Seleukeia on the Tigris. Evidently the closure of Babylon II prompted the transfer of these mint officials via Uncertain Mint 6A to Seleukeia on the Tigris.

Table 9. Recurrent mint controls.

Control	Babylon II	Uncertain Mint 6A
		<i>In the name of Alexander:</i>
⌘	1.3	Series II 125–136; SC 67.5b
		<i>In the name of Seleukos:</i>
⌘	3.1–3.3	Series V, 190–192; SC 69.3
A	2.8, 2.9	Series V, 216–232; SC 69.5–69.7
⌘	1.2–1.19	Series V, 295; SC 69.7

The mint official designated by ⌘

The mint official designated by the ⌘ mint control was a central figure in the mintage of the earliest coinage of Seleukos following his return to Babylon. The Group 1 coinage struck under the mark of this official represents about 70 percent of the Babylon II anchor Alexanders. The same mark is also the primary mint control on the majority of the Seleukid Ba'al/lion staters (SC 88), the output of a separate workshop that is inferred to have operated in parallel with the anchor Alexander emission. This official oversaw the reestablishment of the mint after the Babylonian war, the subsequent expansion of its capacity, after which he appears to have supervised the closure the mint. Briefly his mark appears on the some of the first coinage from Uncertain Mint 6A to bear the name of Seleukos, preceding the same control mark's appearance on some of the earliest issues of the elephant chariot coinage from Seleukeia on the Tigris. The name of this official in the early years of Seleukos ascent to power is unknown. However, the earliest Seleukid coinages of Babylonia and Susa provide some clues, which combined with the historical record provide the basis for a plausible identification of this official.

The monogram ⌘ on type 1.1 can be broken down into the component Greek letters ΠΟΛΥΑΡ (*Polyar*). On subsequent Group 1 issues monogram appears to have been reduced to the letter ⌘ that is a central component of the monogram. Preceding the anchor Alexanders were the Ba'al/lion staters of Seleukos's first satrapy that include an issue bearing the monogram ⌘¹ (a ligature

of Π and P).³⁷ A variant of this ligature, Π̄, then appears as the primary mark on the Susa wreath group (Susa Group 5) coinage of Seleukos³⁸ struck during the Babylonian War. Plausibly these ligatures of Π and P are precursors to the Π̄ mint mark found on the subsequent Babylon II Group 1 emission. Thus, the Π̄, Π̄, Π̄, and Π̄ controls follow in a succession of simplification through the earliest coinage of Seleukos; Π̄ on his satrapal coinage issued in the name of Philip III at the end of his first satrapy at Babylon II, Π̄ on the contemporary lion staters, followed five years later by Π̄ at Susa during the Babylonia War (311/0–309/8 BC), after which the Babylon II Group 1 anchor Alexander coinage commenced with Π̄, immediately succeeded by Π̄ in the period 307/6–304/3 BC.

Based on the monogram deciphered as ΠΟΛΥΑΡ, successively simplified to Π̄, Π̄, and Π̄, the identity of this official could be Polyarchos. Diodorus 19.91.3 records that Polyarchos was in command of a district in Babylonia and joined Seleukos with 1,000 troops when the latter returned to Babylonia in 312/1 BC.³⁹ It appears that Polyarchos was an appointment of Seleukos during his first satrapy, subsequently retained by Antigonos in command of a Babylonian garrison.⁴⁰ Most plausibly, Polyarchos was rewarded for his loyalty to Seleukos and given the responsibility for the latter's coinage issued from Susa in the years of the Babylonian war, and subsequently from Babylon II during Seleukos's eastern anabasis. Certainly, a reasonable argument can be made that the Π̄, Π̄, Π̄ and Π̄ mint marks represent one and the same senior official who moved from Babylon to Susa and then returned to Babylon in the period 311–308 BC. Polyarchos, whose name comes down to us from the ancient sources, is the best candidate we have for the identity of this prominent official.⁴¹

37. Babylon II lion stater ANS 1969.174.4 (318–312 BC); H. Nicolet-Pierre, "Argent et or frappés en Babylonie entre 331 et 311 ou de Mazdai à Séleucos," in *Travaux de numismatique grecque offerts à Georges Le Rider*, ed. M. Amandry and S. Hurter (London: Spink, 1999), 295, no. 18, pl. 29, 18.

38. Taylor, "Wreath Group," for an analysis of Susa Group 5. Formerly attributed to the satrapy of Aspeidas, the Susa Group 5 (Price's "wreath group") coinage is unequivocally dated to the period immediately following Seleukos's annexation of Susiana. It was struck to support Seleukos's campaign against Antigonid forces during the Babylonian War ca. 311/0–309/8 BC; Taylor "Susa," 28.

39. *Diodorus* 19.91.3 He [Seleukos] was joined also by Polyarchus, who had been placed in command of a certain district, with more than a 1,000 soldiers; J. D. Grainger, *Seleukos Nikator: Constructing a Hellenistic Kingdom* (London and New York: Routledge, 2014 reprint of the original 1990 edition), 74 and J. D. Grainger, *The Rise of the Seleukid Empire 323–223 BC* (Barnsley, UK: Pen & Sword History, 2014), 43.

40. R. A. Billows, *Antigonos the One-Eyed and the Creation of the Hellenistic State* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1990), 430, appendix 3, no. 101.

41. I have interpreted the somewhat problematic recut monogram on types 2.10 and 2.11

CATALOGUE

AV Staters

Group 1

Obverse: Head of Athena r. wearing crested Corinthian helmet adorned with coiled serpent.

Reverse: ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Nike standing l. holding wreath and stylis, anchor to l., mint controls beneath left and right wings.

1.4 SC 92; Price 3340 (Serpent on helmet) <LW>

- 1.* Av1 / P1 8.54 BM 1872,0713.30; GC30.3340; SC 92, pl. 5, 92; Houghton MA 4, 38.

Obverse: Head of Athena r. wearing crested Corinthian helmet adorned with gryphon.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ to l., ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Nike standing l. holding wreath and stylis, anchor to l., mint controls beneath left and right wings.

1.10 SC 93.1; Price 3348 (Gryphon on helmet) <LW>

- 2.* Av2 / P2 8.64 ANS 1967.152.300. Av2 almost identical to Av5.
3. Av3 / P3 8.56 SC 93.1, pl. 5, 93.1; CSE 682, pl. 40, 682; Houghton MA 4, 77.

1.10a. SC -; Price - (Gryphon on helmet) <LW>

- 4.* Av3 / P4 8.60 BnF De Clercq 293, RN 1968, pl. II, 293; Houghton MA 4, 78 (corr.). A reversal of the placement of mint controls of SC 93.1 and Price 3348.

to be the result of the cutting of a ligature of pi, rho, kappa over the existing primary control M (Fig. 1). Conceivably, the intended reading of this recut ligature might have included the remnant central component of the underlying M as an inverted lambda in which case the mint mark might have been conceived as ΠΛΡΚ. However, Oliver Hoover has noted (pers. com.) that “In the Greek text of the Diodoros passage, the commander is named Polyarchos, with a chi, rather than Polyarkos, with a kappa. Unless there is a variant tradition in which he is called Polyarkos rather than Polyarchos, the reading of kappa in the complex monogram would seem to make a problem for linking it directly to Polyarchos.” Writing in a Roman world, more than three centuries after the events in Babylonia, it is certainly conceivable that Diodoros’s spelling of the name is a variant form, and that the correct spelling of the name was indeed Polyarkos, rather than Polyarchos. Nonetheless, the identification of the mint official’s name and its possible association with Polyarchos must remain tentative in the absence of more substantial documentary evidence.

1.16 SC 93.2; Price 3352 (Gryphon on helmet) <LW> Γ <RW> Ϙ

5. Av3 / P5 8.52 BnF 1975.252; Houghton MA 4, 51.
 6.* Av4 / P6 8.57 CNG 108 (2018), 275; Goldberg 72 (2013), 4085; Leu 15 (1976), 340; Hess-Leu 11 (1959), 286; Houghton MA 4, 50.

*Group 2***2.1** SC-; Price - (Gryphon on helmet) <LW> Ɱ <RW> Ɱ control recut over A

- 7.* Av5 / P7 8.62 Künker 273 (2016), 251. Av5 almost identical to Av2.

AR Tetradrachms

Obverse: Head of beardless Herakles r. wearing lion skin headdress; dotted border.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ below, ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Zeus *Aëtophoros* seated l. on a high-backed throne, anchor (erased on final rev. dies) and secondary mint control in l. field, primary mint control beneath throne; dotted border.

*Group 1***1.1** SC 80; Price 3339 <LF> - <Th> Ɱ. Zeus's feet rest on a horizontal torch.

- 8.* A1 / P1 16.84 ANS 1944.100.34897; Duyrat *Arados* 980; Houghton MA 4, 186; WSM pl. XLIII, D. A1 is an obverse die link to SC (Part 1) 79, SC (Part 2) CAd43.16, Duyrat *Arados* Group 5, Series 8, 979, Price P153 and WSM pl. XLIII, C in the name of Philip III. A1= Duyrat *Arados* die D228.

1.2 SC 94.1; Price 3342A <LF> Anchor / horizontal club / ΦΙ <Th> Γ

9. A2 / P2 16.93 BM 2002,0101.768.
 10.* A2 / P3 16.72 LWHT Coll.158; VAuctions 215 (2008), 61.
 11. A2 / P3 17.09 CSE II, 43, AHNS 426; Houghton MA 4, 34.

1.3 SC 94.2c; Price 3344A. <LF> Ɱ / anchor <Th> Γ

- 12.* A3 / P4 16.94 BnF 934; Houghton MA 4, 44.
 13.* A4 / P5 17.04 CNG 72 (2006), 887; Commerce ("Seleucus I") Hoard, 2005 (CH 10.265).
 14. A4 / P6 16.98 CNG eAuction 421 (2018), 203. Defaced coin—gouge obliterates anchor.

1.5 SC 94.2b; Price 3341 <LF> Ɱ / anchor <Th> Γ

- 15.* A5 / P7 17.08 Roma Numismatics E-Sale 47 (2018), 348.

16. A6 / P8 17.13 Houghton *MA* 4, 43; Qazvin Hoard (*CH* 1.58), 4.
- 17.* A7 / P9 16.67 CNG 64 (2003), 375; Houghton *MA* 4, 39; AHNS 205; Superior Sale (1986), 1229.
18. A7 / P10 17.2 CGB.fr Monnaies 98 (2011), 98.
19. A7 / P11 15.84 ANS 1944.100.34900; Houghton *MA* 4, 42.
20. A7 / P12 17.08 CNG eAuction 184 (2008), 67.
- 1.6 SC - ; Price 3342 <LF> ☒ / anchor <Th> ☐**
21. A7 / P13 17.12 ANS 1944.100.45125; Houghton *MA* 4, 40; Armenak Hoard (*IGCH* 1423), 122.
22. A7/P13 17.01 Houghton *MA* 4, 41; Meydancikkale Hoard (*CH* 8.308), 2024.
- 1.7 SC - ; Price 3343 <LF> A / anchor <Th> ☐**
- 23.* A8 / P14 16.74 Münzkabinett Berlin 18253723.
- 1.8 SC 94.2a; Price 3344 <LF> Æ / anchor <Th>**
24. A9 / P15 17.18 Goldberg 109 (2019), 2047. P15 - left field mint control recut over the mint control of Type 1.6.
- 25.* A9 / P16 17.15 Münzkabinett Berlin 18253716. P16 left field mint control recut over the mint control of Type 1.6.
26. A9 / P16 16.99 ANS 1944.100.34901; Houghton *MA* 4, 37.
27. A9 / P17 16.68 BM 1886,0610.17; Houghton *MA* 4, 35.
28. A9/P18 16.99 Heritage 3002 (2008), 20044.
29. A9/P19 16.75 Houghton *MA* 4, 36; Sotheby's Sale (30 Apr. 1958).
- 1.9 SC - ; Price - <LF> anchor / ☒ <Th> ☐**
- 30.* A9 / P20 17.00 Roma Numismatics E-Sale 57 (2019), 550.
- 1.11a SC 94.3d; Price 3349 <LF> anchor / ☒ <Th> ☐. Zeus's feet rest on ground line.**
- 31.* A10 / P21 16.77 CNG eAuction 213 (2009), lot 167.
32. A11 / P22 16.83 Bertolami 9 (2014), 230.
33. A11 / P23 16.82 Gitbud & Naumann 23 (2014), 468.
- 34.* A11 / P24 16.82 Ashmolean HCR23646.
- 35.* A12 / P25 17.19 CNG 108 (2018), 276.
- 36.* A13 / P26 16.35 Stacks (28 Apr. 2010), 138; CNG 61 (2002), 793.
- 37.* A14 / P27 17.21 LWHT Coll. 159; Heritage 3022 (2013), 26035.

38. A14 / P28 16.93 CNG eAuction 423 (2018), 192.
 39. A14 / P29 17.06 Heritage 231844 (2018), 61002; Roma Numismatics E-Sale 47 (2018), 350.
 40. A14 / P29 16.96 ANS 1949.88.10; Houghton MA 4, 81.
 41.* A15 / P30 16.00 Kölner 108 (2018), 346.
 42.* A15 / P31 16.60 ANS 1944.100.34907, Houghton MA 4, 82; Mesopotamia Hoard (IGCH 1764).
 43. A16 / P32 17.01 Tauler & Fau 14 (2018), 2050.
 44.* A16 / P33 17.09 Roma Numismatics E-Live 2 (2018), 340.

1.11b SC 94.3d; Price 3349 <LF> anchor <Th> Γ. Zeus's feet rest on footstool.

- 45.* A64 / P34 17.30 Akropolis Ancient Coins inv. no. 19. A64 in advanced state of wear.
 46. A64 / P34 16.67 Rauch E-Live 33 (2020), lot 83.
 47.* A17 / P35 17.18 CNG eAuction 158 (2007), 54.
 48. A17 / P36 17.21 CNG eAuction 308 (2013), 165.
 49.* A18 / P37 16.52 *Künker* 77 (2002), 84.
 50. A19 / P38 16.67 BM 1878,0301.143; Houghton MA 4, 83.
 51.* A19 / P39 16.81 Münzkabinett Berlin 18203072.
 52.* A20 / P39 17.00 CNG 72 (2006), 892; Commerce ("Seleucus I") Hoard, 2005 (CH 10.265).
 53. A20 / P39 16.00 ANS 1944.100.34914.
 54. A20 / P40 17.15 CNG inv. no. 263284.
 55. A20 / P41 16.77 BM 1857,1218.9; Houghton MA 4, 105.
 56. A20 / P41 17.20 Goldberg 84 (2015), 3023.
 57. A20 / P42 17.14 BnF 1966.453.1011.
 58. A20 / P43 16.88 Kölner 106 (2017), 466.
 59. A20 / P43 17.1 ANS 1944.100.34908; Houghton MA 4, 93.
 60.* A21 / P 44 17.10 Solidus Numismatik 29 (2018), 56.
 61. A21 / P45 16.84 CNG 47 (1998), 201.
 62. A21 / P46 16.49 Roma Numismatics E-Sale 38 (2017), 297.
 63. A21 / P47 17.23 CNG eAuction 424 (2018), 247.
 64. A21 / P48 16.71 ANS 1944.100.34916; Houghton MA 4, 94.
 65. A21 / P49 16.30 ANS 1944.100.34915; Houghton MA 4, 95.
 66.* A22 / P50 17.22 ANS 1944.100.45127; Houghton MA 4, 92; Armenak Hoard (IGCH 1423) 124.

67. A23 / P51 16.33 ANS 1944.100.34909; Houghton MA 4, 99; Babylonian 1900 Hoard (*IGCH* 1761).
68. A23 / P52 17.03 Houghton MA 4, 100; Geissener 44 (1989), 233.
69. A23 / P53 n.r. Houghton MA 4, 101.
70. A23 / P54 16.37 ANS 1944.100.34912; Houghton MA 4, 102; Babylonian 1900 Hoard (*IGCH* 1761).
- 71.* A23 / P55 17.22 Pars Coins PCW- G6548.
72. A23 / P56 16.83 CNG 61 (2002), 794.
73. A24 / P57 17.14 Münzkabinett Wien GR 10269.
74. A24 / P58 17.04 BM 2002,0101.770; Hersh Coll.; Houghton MA 4, 85.
- 75.* A24 / P59 16.80 ANS 1944.100.34910; Houghton MA 4, 86.
76. A24 / P60 16.71 Houghton MA 4, 87; Meydancikkale Hoard (*CH* 8.308), 2026.
77. A24 / P60 16.93 CNG eAuction 186 (2008), 41.
- 78.* A25 / P61 16.93 ANS 1944.100.45128; Houghton MA 4, 88; Armenak Hoard (*IGCH* 1423) 125.
- 79.* A26 / P62 16.58 CNG 72 (2006), lot 893; Commerce ("Seleucus I") Hoard, 2005 (*CH* 10.265).
80. A27 / P63 16.29 ANS 1944.100.34913; Houghton MA 4, 79; Babylonian 1900 Hoard (*IGCH* 1761).
- 81.* A27 / P64 17.12 Roma Numismatics E-Live 2 (2018), 338.
- 82.* A28 / P64 17.01 CNG eAuction 223 (2009), 221.
83. A29 / P65 17.13 CGB.fr e-Monnaies Septembre 2016, 403663.
84. A29 / P65 17.18 *CSE* 683; Houghton MA 4, 97.
- 85.* A29 / P66 16.74 Forum Ancient Coins inv. no. SH12222.
- 1.12** SC 94.3c; Price 3346 <LF> anchor / NE <Th> Γ
85. A13 / P67 16.99 Emporium Hamburg 70 (2013), 49.
87. A13 / P68 16.99 CNG eAuction 324 (2014), 179; Wartenberg and Kagan (1999), pl. 42, 48; 1990's Balkan Area Hoard (*CH* 9.196), 48.
- 88.* A13 / P69 17.08 ANS 1944.100.45126; Houghton MA 4, 68; Armenak Hoard (*CH* 1.58) 123.
- 89.* A14 / P70 17.02 VAuctions 265 (2011), 37.
- 90.* A30 / P71 16.88 CNG 60 (2002), 883.

1.13a SC C94.3c; Price - <LF> anchor / $\overline{\text{NE}}$ <Th> Γ . Zeus's feet rest on ground line.

91.	A31 / P72	17.15	Peus 399 (2009), 147; Lanz 135 (2007), 211.
92.	A31 / P73	16.40	ANS 1944.100.34902; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 74; Babylonian 1900 Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1761).
93.	A31 / P74	14.73	ANS 1944.100.34903; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 75; Babylonian 1900 Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1761). Broken coin.
94.*	A31 / P75	17.19	CNG eAuction 323 (2014), 134; CNG 72 (2006), 891; Commerce ("Seleucus I") Hoard, 2005 (<i>CH</i> 10.265).
95.	A31 / P75	16.95	CNG web shop 159606.
96.	A31 / P76	16.83	Gorny & Mosch 261 (2019), 210; Lanz 166 (2018), 66.
97.	A31 / P77	17.13	Gorny & Mosch 212 (2013), 1367.
98.*	A32 / P78	16.89	CNG eAuction 369 (2016), 210.
99.*	A32 / P79	17.05	CNG eAuction 486 (2021), 201. Footstool beneath Zeus's feet.

1.13b SC C94.3c; Price - <LF> anchor, $\overline{\text{NE}}$ <Th> Γ . Zeus's feet rest on footstool.

100.*	A33 / P80	17.12	CNG 94 (2013), 712.
101.	A33 / P80	16.94	Münzkabinett Berlin 18253712.
102.	A33 / P81	17.00	Steven Battelle SKU: U00042.
103.	A33 / P82	16.72	Palmyra Heritage SKU: 123577422092.

1.141 SC 94.3c; Price 3347 <LF> anchor, $\overline{\text{NE}}$ <Th> Γ

104.*	A27 / P83	17.07	BM 1878,0301.141; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 76.
105.	A27 / P84	16.82	Rauch 86, (2010), 389.
106.	A33 / P85	17.07	<i>CSE</i> II, 44 (AHNS 114); Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 69.
107.	A33 / P85	17.07	Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 70; Meydancikkale Hoard (<i>CH</i> 8.308), 2030.
108.	A33 / P86	16.99	Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 71; Meydancikkale Hoard (<i>CH</i> 8.308), 2031. A33 recut (?) based on <i>MA</i> 4 comment.
109.	A34 / P87	16.36	Münzkabinett Berlin 18253713.
110.	A34 / P88	17.19	CNG eAuction 132 (2006), 69.
111.*	A34 / P89	16.01	ANS 1942.37.1; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 73.
112.	A34 / P90	17.00	Gitbud & Naumann 20 (2014), 122.
113.	A34 / P91	17.12	CNG eAuction 150 (2006), 150.
114.	A34 / P91	17.09	CNG 72 (2006), 890; Commerce ("Seleucus I") Hoard, 2005 (<i>CH</i> 10.265).

1.15 SC 94.3b; Price 3351 <LF> anchor, ⷈ <Th> Γ

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|-------|------------|-------|---|
| 115. | A35 / P92 | 17.00 | Numismatik Naumann 51 (2017), 211. |
| 116. | A35 / P92 | 17.01 | CNG eAuction 438 (2019), 190. |
| 117.* | A35 / P93 | 16.99 | CNG 72 (14 Jun 2006), lot 889; Commerce ("Seleucus I") Hoard, 2005 (<i>CH</i> 10.265). |
| 118.* | A36 / P94 | 16.77 | Münzkabinett Berlin 18253711. |
| 119. | A37 / P95 | 17.10 | BM 1878,0301.14; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 63; Price 3351. |
| 120. | A37 / P96 | 16.31 | ANS 1944.100.34906; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 64. |
| 121. | A37 / P97 | 17.26 | Münzkabinett Berlin 18253710. |
| 122.* | A37 / P98 | 16.85 | ANS 1952.123.189; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 62; Cavalla 1951 Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 0450). |
| 123. | A37 / P99 | 16.65 | ANS 1949.88.9; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 65. |
| 124. | A37 / P100 | 17.14 | Houghton <i>MA</i> 4 60; Qazvin Hoard (<i>CH</i> 1.58), 5. |
| 125. | A37 / P100 | 16.61 | BM 2002,0101.771; Hersh Coll.; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 61. |

1.17 SC 94.3a; Price 3353 <LF> anchor, ⷈ <Th> Γ

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|-------|------------|-------|--|
| 126.* | A37 / P101 | 16.79 | BM 1869,0601.1; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 59. |
| 127. | A37 / P102 | 16.54 | Peus E-Auction 4 (2017), 106. |
| 128.* | A38 / P103 | 17.13 | CNG eAuction 412 (2018), 254; CNG eAuction 224 (2009), 263. |
| 129. | A38 / P104 | 17.11 | CNG 72 (2006), 888; Commerce ("Seleucus I") Hoard, 2005 (<i>CH</i> 10.265). |
| 130. | A38 / P105 | 17.06 | Numismatik Naumann 72 (2018), 247. |
| 131. | A38 / P105 | 16.99 | CNG eAuction 433 (2018), 104; CNG eAuction 406 (2017), 448. |
| 132. | A38 / P105 | 16.76 | CNG eAuction 422 (2018), 285. |
| 133. | A38 / P106 | 17.03 | Heritage 3049 (2016), 32168. |
| 134. | A38 / P106 | 17.10 | CNG 45 (1998), 207. |
| 135. | A38 / P107 | 17.18 | Lanz 166 (2018), 67; CNG eAuction 403 (2017), 238. |
| 136. | A38 / P108 | 15.68 | ANS 1944.100.34904; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 52. |
| 137. | A38 / P109 | 16.80 | Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 53; Meydancikkale Hoard (<i>CH</i> 8.308), 2033. |
| 138. | A38 / P109 | 17.00 | Goldberg 85 (2015), 301. |
| 139.* | A39 / P110 | 16.87 | ANS 1944.100.34905; Houghton <i>MA</i> 4, 54. |
| 140.* | A40 / P111 | 16.98 | Roma Numismatics E-Sale 54 (2019), 308. |
| 141. | A40 / P112 | 16.37 | Münzkabinett Berlin 18253714. |

142. A40 / P113 16.94 BnF 935; Houghton MA 4, 55.
 143. A40 / P113 16.80 Houghton MA 4, 56; SNG Copenhagen, Macedonia 791.
 144. A40 / P114 16.85 Houghton MA 4, 57; Meydancikkale Hoard (*CH* 8.308), 2032.
 145. A40 / P115 17.15 Houghton MA 4, 58 (AHNS 339).
 146.* A41 / P116 16.92 CNG eAuction 165 (2007), 53.
 147.* A42 / P117 17.16 The New York Sale (2012), 1037.
 148.* A43 / P118 16.81 NBJ Numismatics - VAuctions 355 (2020), 16.
 149.* A44 / P119 16.66 CNG eAuction 308 (2013), 164; Wartenberg and Kagan (1999), p. 398, 49; 1990's Balkan Area Hoard (*CH* 9.196), 49. Left field monogram illegible.

1.18 SC -; Price - <LF> anchor erased, <Th> Γ

- 150.* A29 / P120 17.00 ANS 1947.98.294; Houghton MA 4, 103.

1.19 SC -; Price - <LF> Anchor erased, <Th> Γ

- 151.* A34 / P121 17.29 LWHT Coll. 160; Spink Numismatic Circular CXVIII (2010), No. 1, GK2870.

Group 2

2.2 SC 94.6a corr.; Price - <LF> anchor,) <Th> M

- 152.* A45 / P122 17.02 BM 2002.0101.774; Houghton MA 4, 22 (corr.).
 153. A45 / P123 n.r. Houghton MA 4, 23 (corr); Peus 274 (1970), 1644.

2.3 SC-; Price - <LF> anchor, <Th> M

154. A45 / P124 17.24 Pars Coins PCW-G6269.
 155. A45 / P124 16.75 Noble Numismatics 120 (2019), 3020.
 156.* A45 / P125 17.30 CNG eAuction 156 (2007), 64.

2.4 SC 94.6b; Price 3359 <LF> anchor, A <Th> M

157. A46 / P126 16.46 Herbert Grün 55 (2011), 23.
 158.* A46 / P127 16.83 ANS 1944.100.77105; Houghton MA 4, 5. Babylonian 1900 Hoard (*IGCH* 1761).
 159. A46 / P128 17.10 Noble Numismatics 65 (2000), 1827.
 160. A46 / P129 17.08 Houghton MA 4, 7; Meydancikkale Hoard (*CH* 8.308), 2035.
 161. A46 / P130 15.21 ANS 1944.100.77102. Heavily corroded.

162. A47 / P131 17.18 Roma Numismatics E-Sale 70 (2020), 814; Roma E-Live 3 (2018), 338.
- 163.* A47 / P131 17.18 CNG 94 (2013), 713; CNG 72 (2006), 895; Commerce ("Seleucus I") Hoard, 2005 (*CH* 10.265).
164. A47 / P131 16.90 BM 1878,0301.146; Houghton *MA* 4, 1.
165. A47 / P131 17.00 Houghton *MA* 4, 2; Meydancikkale Hoard (*CH* 8.308), 2036.
166. A47 / P132 16.20 Praefectus Coins SKU: GRA3657.
167. A47 / P133 17.20 Münzkabinett Berlin 18253721.
- 168.* A48 / P134 16.78 BM 1878,0301.144; Houghton *MA* 4, 3.
- 169.* A49 / P135 17.08 CNG 72 (2006), 896; Commerce ("Seleucus I") Hoard, 2005 (*CH* 10.265).
170. A49 / P136 16.80 CNG eAuction 439 (2019), 113.
171. A49 / P136 17.05 CNG eAuction 424 (2018), 248; CNG 41 (1997), 301.
172. A49 / P137 17.12 Stack's Coin Galleries (2007), 42.
173. A49 / P137 17.03 Heritage 3054 (2017), 32059.
174. A49 / P137 16.96 Palmyra Heritage SKU: 123668078421.
- 175.* A50 / P138 17.01 LWHT Coll. 163; ex William K. Raymond Collection.
176. A50 / P139 16.91 Houghton *MA* 4, 9; Meydancikkale Hoard (*CH* 8.308), 2038.
- 177.* A51 / P140 16.91 ANS 1944.100.77103; Houghton *MA* 4, 10.
178. A51 / P140 17.19 Münzkabinett Berlin 18253722.
179. A51 / P141 16.93 Roma Numismatics (May 2013), 350.
- 180.* A52 / P142 17.30 Noble Numismatics 65 (2000), 1745.
181. A52 / P143? 15.49 Miller (2010), pl. 8, 41; East Arachosia (Quetta) Hoard, 2002 (*CH* 10.275), 41.
- 182.* A53 / P143 16.40 ANS 1944.100.77101; Houghton *MA* 4, 11; *WSM* pl. XLIV, A.

2.5 SC 94.6b; Price 3358 <LF> anchor, Λ <Th> M

- 183.* A46 / P144 17.06 BM 2002,0101.773; Hersh Coll.
184. A46 / P144 17.18 Heritage 3004 (2009), 22870.
- 185.* A47 / P145 16.92 Roma Numismatics E-Sale 34 (2017), 112.

2.6 SC 94.6c: Price 3356A (drachm) <LF> anchor, W <Th> M

- 186.* A54 / P146 17.10 LWHT Coll. 164; ex William K. Raymond Collection.

2.7 SC 94.6c; Price 3356 <LF> anchor, $\overline{\text{P}}$ <Th> M

- 187.* A54 / P147 17.10 BM 1878,0301.142; Houghton MA 4, 24 ; Price 3356.
 188. A54 / P147 17.27 Houghton MA 4, 25.
 189. A54 / P148 17.10 CSE II, 45 (AHNS 206); Houghton MA 4, 26; Superior Sale (1986), 26.
 190. A54 / P149 16.95 Houghton MA 4, 27; Meydancikkale Hoard (CH 8.308), 2034.
 191. A54 / P150 15.89 ANS 1944.100.77104; Houghton MA 4, 28; Babylonian 1909 Hoard (IGCH 1761).
 192. A54 / P151 17.09 Heritage 231849 (2018), 61040.
 193. A54 / P152 17.13 ANS 1944.100.77106; Houghton MA 4, 29.
 194. A55 / P153 17.06 Münzkabinett Berlin 18207745.
 195. A55 / P153 n.r. Teutoburger 90 (2015), 2034.
 196.* A55 / P153 17.09 CNG eAuction 300 (2014), 72; Wartenberg and Kagan (1999), pl. 42, 50; 1990s Balkan Area Hoard (CH 9.196), 50.
 197. A55 / P154 17.02 CNG eAuction 381 (2016), 222.
 198. A56 / P155 16.97 Gärtner 32 (2015), 34132.
 199. A56 / P155 n.r. Oeconomides (1998), pl. 65, 42; Tricala Hoard, 42.
 200.* A57 / P156 17.13 Hirsch 309 (2015), 113.
 201. A58 / P157 17.02 Numismatik Naumann 60 (2017), 244.
 202.* A58 / P157 16.93 CNG eAuction 220 (2009), 178.
 203. A58 / P158 16.85 Roma Numismatics E-Sale 57 (2019), 551.
 204. A58 / P159 17.10 CNG 72 (2006), 897; Commerce ("Seleucus I") Hoard, 2005 (CH 10.265).

2.8 SC - ; Price 3350 <LF> anchor, $\overline{\text{A}}$ <Th> A. Zeus's feet rest on ground line.

205. A59 / P160 16.95 Heritage 231850 (2018), 62045.
 206.* A59 / P160 17.06 Triskeles 25 (2018), 130; Pars Coins PCW- G6213.
 207.* A60 / P161 17.16 LWHT Coll 161; Pars Coins PCW-G4381.
 208. A60 / P162 17.28 Roma Numismatics E-Live 2 (2018), 339.
 209. A60 / P163 17.16 Houghton MA 4, 112; Qazvin Hoard (CH 1.58), 11.
 210. A60 / P164 16.53 BM 1888,0614.51; Houghton MA 4, 110.
 211. A60 / P165 16.38 Rauch Summer (2010), 216.
 212. A60 / P166 17.20 Houghton MA 4, 111; Münzen und Medaillen FPL 333 (1972), 20.

213. A60 / P167 16.67 Heritage 231530 (2015), 64004.
- 2.9 SC 94.4; Price - <LF> anchor, $\overline{\text{A}}$ <Th> A. Zeus's feet rest on footstool.**
- 214.* A61 / P168 16.99 Roma Numismatics (May 2013), 349.
215. A61 / P169 15.89 Noble Numismatics 121 (2019), 4338.
216. A61 / P170 16.17 Rauch eAuction 9 (2011), 97.
217. A61 / P170 16.75 ANS 1944.100.34922; Houghton MA 4, 120.
218. A61 / P171 16.63 Münzkabinett Berlin 18253703.
219. A61 / P172 17.00 Heritage Europe 52 (2016), 227.
220. A61 / P173 15.80 ANS 1944.100.34921; Houghton MA 4, 121; Babylonian 1900 Hoard (IGCH 1761). Heavily corroded coin—light weight.
221. A61 / P174 16.19 CNG eAuction 168 (2007), 67.
- 222.* A62 / P175 17.02 ANS 1944.100.34918; Houghton MA 4, 109; Zemun 1929 Hoard (IGCH 0458).
- 223.* A63 / P175 16.67 ANS 1944.100.34920; Houghton MA 4, 118.
224. A63 / P176 17.00 Houghton MA 4, 119; Meydancikkale Hoard (CH 8.308), 2021.
225. A63 / P177 17.05 Heritage 231811 (2018), 63015.
- 226.* A64 / P177 17.09 CNG eAuction 263 (2011), 131. A64 unworn, in earliest state.
227. A64 / P178 17.05 Gorny & Mosch 265 (2019), 224.
228. A64 / P178 16.84 Warszawskie Centrum Numizmatyczne 54 (2013), lot 7.
229. A64 / P178 16.36 Künker 23 (2013), 20.
230. A64 / P179 17.11 CNG eAuction 422 (2018), 286.
231. A64 / P180 17.03 Houghton MA 4, 116; Dewing Coll. 2577.
232. A64 / P181 17.03 BnF 931.
233. A64 / P182 16.21 ANS 1944.100.34919; Houghton MA 4, 115; Babylonian 1900 Hoard (IGCH 1761).
- 2.10 SC -; Price - <LF> anchor, Λ <Th> - $\overline{\text{A}}$ recut over M**
- 234.* A60 / P183 17.07 Heritage 231902 (2019), 62012.
- 2.11 SC 94.5; Price - <LF> anchor and control erased <Th> $\overline{\text{A}}$ recut over M**
- 235.* A60 / P183 16.94 LWHT Coll. 162; ex William K. Raymond Collection. P183 anchor and mint control erased from left field.

2.12 SC 94.5; Price - <LF> anchor and control erased <Th> □ recut over A

236. A60 / P184 16.88 Houghton *MA* 4, 107; Meydancikkale Hoard (*CH* 8.308), 2028.
237. A60 / P185 17.15 Houghton *MA* 4, 108; Meydancikkale Hoard (*CH* 8.308), 2023.

2.13 SC 94.4; Price 3350 <LF> anchor and control erased <Th> A

238. A65 / P186 16.49 Houghton *MA* 4, 122; Meydancikkale Hoard (*CH* 8.308), 2022.

*Group 3***3.1** SC 105.1; Price 3363 <LF> ⋈ / anchor <Th> ⚭

- 239.* A66 / P187 17.13 Heritage 231712 (2017), 64009.
240. A66 / P188 17.09 *Künker* 153 (2009), 8241.
241. A66 / P189 16.85 BM 1880,0508.1; Price 3363; Houghton *MA* 4, 180.
242. A66 / P190 16.97 Münzkabinet Berlin 18253837.
243. A66 / P190 16.61 ANS 1944.100.34898; Houghton *MA* 4, 181; Babylonian 1900 Hoard (*IGCH* 1761). Anchor and mint control barely visible in highly corroded left field.

3.2 SC 105.2 corr.; Price 3363A corr. <LF> ⋈ , ⚭ / anchor <Th> ⚮

- 244.* A67 / P191 16.28 ANS 1944.100.34899; Houghton *MA* 4, 182; Babylonian 1900 Hoard (*IGCH* 1761).

3.3 SC 105.2 corr.; Price - <LF> Left field anchor and control erased <Th> ⚮

245. A66 / P192 16.84 Houghton *MA* 4, 189; Meydancikkale Hoard (*CH* 8.308), 2020.

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GUIDE TO PLATE 10 COINS

- A. ANS 1947.98.295.
- B. ANS 1944.100.77079.
- C. ANS 1944.100.77080.
- D. LWHT Coll. 196; Heritage 3015 (2011), 25927.
- E. LWHT Coll. 200; ex Houghton Coll., CSE 938.
- F. Pars Coins PCW-G6372.
- G. LWHT Coll. 309; Pars Coins PCW-G6328.
- H. Roma Numismatics E-Live 1 (2018), 282
- I. NBJ Numismatics sku-g18.
- J. LWHT Coll. 311; Roma Numismatics XVI (2018), 383.

42. <http://numismatics.org/pella/> accessed 18 November 2019.

43. <https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0/> accessed 18 November 2019.

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Table 2. Tetracharm die links.

Group 1		Groups 2 and 3	
SC 79; Price P153 ⊕ I		First Satrapy of Seleukos	
[A1]	1.1 — ⊕	3.1 ⋈ ⊕	
[A7]	1.5 ⊕ Γ	A66	
[A9]	1.6 ⊕ Γ	[A45]	2.2 ⊕ M
1.8 ⊕ Γ	[A9]	[A46, A47]	2.3 ⊕ M
1.9 ⊕ Γ	[A9]	[A54]	2.4 AM
			2.5 ⊕ M
			2.6 ⊕ M
			2.7 ⊕ M
[A13, A14]	1.11a ⊕ Γ		
	1.12 NE Γ		
[A27]	1.11b ⊕ Γ — A64	[A60]	2.8 ⊕ A
[A33]	1.13b ⊕ Γ		2.9 ⊕ A
[A37]	1.14 ⊕ Γ		
[A29]	1.15 ⊕ Γ		
[A34]	1.17 ⊕ Γ		
<i>Anchor erased from reverse dies</i>		[A60]	2.10 ⊕ ⊕
	1.18 ⊕ Γ	[A60]	2.11 — ⊕
	1.19 ⊕ Γ		2.12 — Γ
			3.3 — ⊕
			P183

Table 4. Sequence chart.

Group 1		Group 3	
1.1	-, ⊕		
1.2	club/ Φ Γ		
<i>Mint control above anchor flukes</i>		<i>Mint control above anchor</i>	
1.3	⊥ Γ	3.1	⊥ Δ
1.4	⊥ Γ (stater)	3.2	⊥ Δ ⊕
1.5	⊥ Γ		
1.6	⊥ Γ		
1.7	A Γ		
1.8	⊥ Γ		
<i>Mint control below anchor stock</i>		Group 2	
1.9	⊥ Γ	<i>Mint control to r. of anchor</i>	
		2.1	⊥ Γ (stater)
		2.2	⊥. M
		2.3	⊥ M
1.10	⊥ Γ (stater)	2.4	A M
		2.5	Λ M
1.11a	⊥ Γ 1.12 NE Γ	2.6	Ω M
		2.7	⊥. M
		2.8	⊥ A
	1.13a ⊥ Γ	<i>Footstool beneath Zeus's feet</i>	
	1.13a ⊥ Γ	2.9	⊥ A
<i>Mint control to r. of anchor shank</i>			
1.11b	⊥ Γ 1.13b ⊥ Γ	1.15	⊥ Γ
	1.14 ⊕ Γ	1.16	⊥ Γ (stater)
		1.17	⊥ Γ
		<i>Recycled and recut dies</i>	
		2.10	Λ ⊥ Γ recut over M
<i>Anchor symbol erased from dies</i>		<i>Anchor symbol erased</i>	
1.18	⊥ Γ 1.19 ⊕ Γ	2.11	— ⊥ Γ recut over M
		2.12	— Γ recut over A
		2.13	— A
		3.3	— ⊕

Plates

AV Staters

Group 1AR Tetradrachms

Plate 2

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31

34

35

36

37

41

42

44

45

47

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52

60

66

71

75

Plate 4

78

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81

82

85

88

89

90

94

The Anchor Alexanders of Babylon II

98

99

100

104

111

117

118

122

126

Plate 6

128

139

140

146

147

148

149

150

151

The Anchor Alexanders of Babylon II

Group 2 AR Tetradrachms

152

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158

163

168

169

175

177

180

Plate 8

182

183

185

186

187

196

200

202

206

207

214

222

223

226

234

235

Group 3 AR Tetradrachms

239

244

Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis)

A. SC 67.5c

B. SC 67.6

C. SC 67.6

D. SC 69.4

E. SC 69.7

Susa

F. Susa 7.7

G. Susa 7.8

H. Susa 7.8

I. Susa 7.10

J. Susa 7.11

